

Abar-B's comparatively lower seed protein would not be detrimental to growth and development. Thus Abar-B can safely be recommended for extensive cultivation and large-scale consumption in this region. ❧

Intan – a blast-resistant semidwarf rice for Karnataka, India

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Intan was an experimental line from Indonesia in a set of more than 1,000 rices screened for blast resistance at the Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, by scientists of the University of Agricultural Sciences in collaboration with the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project and IRRI. In the kharif seasons of 1969 and 1970, Intan emerged as resistant to blast. Its other special features included intermediate height, improved plant type, late maturity, and fine grain quality. It was tested in the state coordination multilocation variety trials from 1971 to 1973 at Ponnampet, Mercara, Sirsi, and Mugad and on a private farm at Mudigere where no paddy could thrive due to severe blast. Intan was compared with popular local varieties KB 356, BKB, T141, Y 4, Puttabhatha, and the new varieties IR8, IR20, Pankaj, Jagannath, Mahsuri, Vijaya, and Manohansali. Not only was the resistance of Intan confirmed, it also yielded from 20 to 30% higher than the others. The yield increase was enormous in situations where blast was severe.

District trials were conducted in farmers' fields during 1973 in 0.4-ha (1-acre) plots to compare Intan with varieties such as KB 356, Puttabhatha, IE 20, S 701, Jaya, Hanagal Rajohog, and S 1092. The yield increase ranged from 4 to 37%, averaging 20%, even under submanagement situations. In 1974 and 1975, Intan yielded as high as 7.5 t/ha.

In 1975 the State Variety Evaluation Committee released Intan for commercial cultivation in the valleys of the hilly region. In 1977 the Committee recommended it for cultivation in the

lowlands of the direct-seeded tract. More than 12 ha of Intan were drill-sown in paddy block demonstrations organized by the State Department of Agriculture in Hassan District and were a great success.

Intan is photosensitive and grows to 100–125 cm in plains or hills. It grows fairly tall in coastal climate. The stems and leaves have purple pigmentation, which varies in intensity with altitude and season. The panicle is dense and partially droopy, bearing medium-slender, apiculus, and pigmented grains. It matures in 160–175 days. The CFTRI, Mysore, has reported that this rice is ideally suited for parboiling. Other reported merits are suitability to waterlogged conditions; good

performance even under low fertility levels; higher brown rice recovery and grain storage quality; less milling breakage; and tolerance to short-duration floods.

Intan has been well accepted by farmers in the hilly and direct-seeded regions of Karnataka. A successful ratoon crop was raised, producing about 2 t/ha with no fertilizers and with limited seepage water, at the Agricultural Research Station, Mercara. Some farmers have also reported ratooning Intan. The variety is capable of replacing any lowland late-maturing type and is ideally suited for blast-endemic areas. Even in the plains of Mysore and Hassan districts, Intan has replaced late local types such as S 1092 and S 749 and is spreading fast. ❧

Comparison of farmers' conditions, scientists' breeding efforts, and latest varieties

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IRRI attempted to obtain a measure of the relevance of scientists' research efforts in providing the types of varieties that farmers need in a study of rice breeding programs conducted in collaboration with Iowa State University, USA, and partially funded by the Rockefeller Foundation.

Each of 23 rice breeders at 22 experiment stations and universities in 8 Asian countries was asked 3 questions:

1) What percentage of the rice grown in farmers' fields within the area served by that experiment station was irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, and deep-water or floating rice?

2) What percentage of the scientist's professional time was spent in

improvement of irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, and deep-water or floating rice?

3) What percentage of all varieties released by that station over the past 5 years was suited for each of the 4 rice-growing conditions? To eliminate bias, the sequence of the three questions was dispersed among other questions in the survey.

The breeders perceived a mean of 43% of the rice grown on farmers' fields as irrigated. They spent a mean of 60% of their time working on irrigated rice and considered 57% of all varieties released by their stations over the previous 5 years as suitable for irrigated conditions (see table). Although 40% of the farmers' fields were cited as rainfed lowland, the scientists spent 22% of their time in that area and considered 32% of the recently released varieties suitable for rainfed conditions. Upland rice occupied

Rice breeders' perceptions of the rice-growing conditions in farmers' fields in the regions served by experiment stations, the mean percentages of research efforts that rice breeders devote to rices for those conditions, and the varieties released over the past 5 years. Twenty-three rice breeders for 23 regions served by 22 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 8 Asian nations, 1975.

Item	Irrigated	Rice-growing condition (%)		
		Rainfed lowland	Upland	Deep-water or floating
Farmers' fields	43	40	12	5
Scientists' research efforts	60	22	14	4
Newest varieties ^a	57	32	10	2

^a Released over the past 5 years

12% of farmers' fields, scientists devoted 14% of their time to it, and 10% of the recently released varieties were suitable for upland conditions. For deep-water and floating rice, the mean percentages were: farmers' conditions, 5%; scientists' time, 4%; and latest varieties, 2%.

Two promising IRYN cultures

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During September 1976, 29 medium-duration cultures of the International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) and check varieties IR8, IR26, and IR20 were received for tests at Aduthurai through the International Rice Testing Program. The materials were sown on 29 September and transplanted on 29 October.

Performance of rices in the International Rice Yield Nursery, Aduthurai, India.

Variety	Parentage	yield (t/ha)	Yield compared with that of IR20 (%)	Days to flowering	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle (no./hill)	Panicle wt (g)
IET 4094 (CR 156-5021-207)	BU 1/CR 115	9.0	178.5	95	69	8.3	1.21
P 881-19-22-12 IB-6-IB	IR22//IR930-147-8/Col. 1	8.7	173.0	103	73	4.0	1.77
IR8	Peta/DGWG	3.8	74.6	104	79	5.4	2.00
IR26	IR24/TKM 6	4.2	82.6	104	77	5.9	1.43
IR20	IR262/TKM 6	5.0	100.0	105	91	6.9	1.97
CD (P=0.05)	—	3.6	71.1	—	—	—	—

IET 4094 and P 881-19-22-12-IB-6-IB were superior to the checks, yielding 9.0 and 8.7 t/ha in 125 and 133 days, respectively. They are semidwarf cultures with long slender grain. IET 4094 was moderately resistant to stem borers and leaf folders, and susceptible to

bacterial streak, helminthosporium, and bacterial blight diseases. P 881 was resistant to stem borers; moderately resistant to leaf folders, bacterial blight, and helminthosporium; and susceptible to bacterial streak.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Experimental induction of rice tungro virus epiphytotic

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A field technique to screen rice against tungro virus has been developed at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, Orissa, India. The technique is based on the transitory virus transmission, rapid buildup, and quick movement of the vectors.

Plants were successfully infected under field conditions by manipulating the vector population, introducing a source of virus inoculum, and planting susceptible rices. Sowing and transplanting of rice were timed to coincide with the natural buildup of leafhoppers. To attract vectors to the experimental plots, planting was delayed from 4 to 6 weeks. Two rows of Taichung Native 1, which is highly susceptible to

leafhoppers and tungro virus, were alternated with two test lines. A starter inoculum of as much as 1% of preinoculated seedlings of Jaya was evenly distributed. Within 30 to 40 days, 100% of the susceptible varieties were infected. Out of more than 10,000 varieties and hybrid lines screened over the past 5 years, more than 100 were identified as resistant.

Rice tungro virus disease - resistance and control

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Tungro, one of the most devastating virus diseases of rice, occurs in epidemic form in India, the Philippines, Bangladesh,

Thailand, Indonesia, and Malaysia. Losses in susceptible rices often exceed 60%. Almost 50 resistant cultivars were identified in an extensive screening program of about 5,000 tall indigenous varieties over a 4-year period at CRR. The rices were not high yielders and were sensitive to lodging. The resistance genes are now being transferred from the donors to stiff-strawed semidwarf cultivars in an international breeding program. A few high yielding varieties, such as IR20, IR30, Pusa 2-21, Ratna, Annapurna, and Pankaj were found to be tolerant.

Tungro can also be controlled through control of its leafhopper vectors. In field and greenhouse experiments on 14 insecticides, carbofuran (Furadan 3G), at 2 kg a.i./ha at 15-day intervals, effectively controlled the disease and its vectors. Other insecticides effectively controlled the vectors, but failed to check the disease.